

WHEN TWO BECOME ONE: THE EXPERIENCES OF STUDENTS IN A SINGLE-PARENT HOUSEHOLD

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When Two Become One: The Experiences of Students in a Single-Parent Household

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Abstract

Despite extensive studies on academic achievement, the unique challenges and resilience of students from single-parent households remain underexplored. Through purposive sampling, this phenomenological research explored the lived experiences of nine (9) senior high school students from a well-known performing arts school in Quezon City who grew up in a single-parent household. A researcher-made interview protocol with ten (10) open-ended questions that was validated by renowned experts was administered to gather responses and sufficient, vital information from the participants. With the utilization of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis, three (3) superordinate themes were generated: (1) challenges encountered which delves to the emotional, supportive and financial encounters of the participants; (2) experiences of growing up in a single parent household which pertains to the new responsibilities alongside with the bullying and social challenges faced by the participants; and, (3) emotional well-being which covers the participants' emotional struggles, negative outlook on personal future and their hopes for future family life.

Keywords: *single-parent household, senior high school students, lived experiences*

Introduction

The issue of the experiences of children in single-parent households received a great deal of attention in understanding family structures for child development. Numerous studies explored the psychological, social, and academic outcomes of children growing up in single parent households and highlighted the challenges they faced (Emmen et al., 2021). There were many factors why families led to having single parents such as divorce, death, separation, cheating, or personal choice. Such households presented unique circumstances that could have significant implications for children's experiences, including their academic achievements, social interaction, and overall emotional well-being (De Castro, 2023).

Single-parent households increased and became commonplace around the world. Today, nearly 24 million children in the United States lived in single-parent households. This number had been increasing for half a century, and affected about one in three children across the United States. This increase was driven by several long-term demographic trends, including late marriage, declining marriage rates, rising divorce rates, and increasing numbers of children born to unmarried mothers (Casey, 2022). Despite the increasing number of single-parent households, there was a notable gap in the literature regarding the experiences of students from these households. While some studies explored the general effects of single parenthood on children's outcomes and focused on the cause of being in a single parent household and few specifically examined the unique challenges and opportunities faced by students from single-parent households from most of what the researcher read in various literature and articles related to this study (Malima et al., n.d.).

Single-parent households increased and became common globally. According to a study by Casey (2022), there were 101.3 million single parents around the world. Additionally, the average single parent rate was 7%, less than one-third of the overall rate in the United States. In the Philippines, single-parent households had also become common. According to De Castro (2023), the number of single parents in the Philippines was currently estimated at 14 to 15 million. The structure of the traditional Filipino family, one that consisted of a mother, father, and children, had evolved significantly in recent decades. The number of children growing up in single-parent households was increasing.

A single-parent family was defined as a family in which one parent, either a mother or father, lived, was supposed to take care of their child, and was responsible for raising their child. These kinds of households often faced various challenges and problems compared to a normal household that consisted of two parents. The problems ranged from financial constraints, limited time for parenting, and a potential lack of emotional support for children (Kramer, 2019).

Understanding the experiences of students from single-parent households was essential for several reasons. Children growing up in these kinds of households often faced various challenges that may have been caused by a lack of emotional support from parents. These problems may also have led to various educational challenges such as lower academic achievement, increased dropout rates, and reduced access to resources. Exploring these experiences could shed light on the factors influencing educational outcomes and inform interventions to support these students (Casey, 2022).

Research Questions

When defining the term family, there were many definitions from different perspectives. Knowing so, this study aimed to explore the experiences of students who grew up in a single-parent household. More so, this intended to identify the challenges they have encountered alongside with their emotional well-being. By examining the unique circumstances and support system available to senior high school students, this study aimed to explore the experiences of students in a single-parent household, specifically answering the following questions:

1. What are the unique challenges encountered by the student growing up in a single-parent household?
2. What are the experiences of the student growing up in a single-parent household?
3. How was the emotional well-being of students in a single-parent household?

Literature Review

A global trend had been the rise in single-parent families, and it was critical to comprehend the effects this had on the kids who grew up in these homes. The disadvantages that kids in single-parent households suffered had been addressed in several studies.

The correlation between adolescent crime rates and single-parent families was one important discovery (Kroese et al., 2021). This implied that young people from single-parent families could need more professional advice and support to become resilient and deal with obstacles in their life.

Another area where children in single-parent households could require extra assistance was in their academic achievement. According to research, teenagers from single-parent households needed additional help and guidance in order to perform better academically (Yee et al., 2017). It was important to note, nevertheless, that children living with divorced single mothers might perform better academically when family background was not considered, whereas children living with divorced single fathers might perform worse (Zhang, 2020).

Being a single parent had advantages despite these difficulties. Children and parents who spent quality time together might develop a unique bond that might even be stronger than in non-single-parent households (Wolf, 2019). Children in single-parent households also frequently received assistance from their extended families or local organizations, which could significantly improve their quality of life.

Children who lived in single-parent households might experience a variety of negative outcomes. They might face social dangers such as material squalor, poverty, and a difficult work-life balance (Maldonado & Nieuwenhuis, 2019). Additionally, behavioral issues, emotional disruptions, and subpar academic performance might be present in kids living in single-parent households (Adegboyega, 2018). In addition, kids who lived with a single parent might experience insecurity, loneliness, and immature behavior (Fatima et al., 2021). The mental health of children living in single-parent households could also be negatively impacted by maternal depression (Leung et al., 2023).

The effects on children living in single-parent households could also be influenced by factors including socioeconomic status and family dysfunction. Bullying and other adversities might be more likely to affect children from low-income homes and those who had experienced family dysfunction (Fraga et al., 2022).

However, it was crucial to remember that parental involvement significantly affected children's academic success and general wellbeing. Adolescents' psychological ties to school and academic achievement had been proven to be positively impacted by positive interactions with parents and peers (Bradley et al., 2019). Academic achievement could also be influenced by parents' involvement in their kids' education, both at home and in the community (Single parenting and today's family, 2019).

With this, children who grew up in a single-parent household might face difficulties, including possible repercussions on their social and scholastic development. Children in single-parent households could, however, thrive and overcome these difficulties with the appropriate support, direction, and involvement from parents and the community.

Methodology

Research Design

Phenomenology is a qualitative research approach that centered on exploring an individual's lived experiences within their world (Neubauer et al., 2019). The study of the lived experiences of Senior High School students in Lucrecia R. Kasilag who had single parents was presented using phenomenological qualitative research to see how it affected their academic achievement. Although the experience could not be extended to a wider audience, the study could produce an important understanding of feelings and experiences. The researcher wanted to answer the central question: "What were the lived experiences of Senior High School students in Lucrecia R. Kasilag who has single parents?"

Participants

This study involved nine (9) respondents from grade 11 and grade 12 students currently enrolled in Lucrecia R. Kasilag Senior High School for the School Year 2023-2024. The respondents were chosen regardless of their strand or age but had to fit with the purpose of the study to explore the lived experiences of students in a single-parent household. The respondents had to be living in a single-parent household for at least two years.

Instrument

Profile Survey Sheet

The researchers used a profile survey sheet to obtain the profile of the participants. Profile survey was a survey comprised of questions

that were used to determine the demographic data points of respondents specifically their highest educational attainment, school they attended to, and type of family structure they belonged to know if they were eligible to provide the data needed in the study (QuestionPro, n.d.).

Researcher-made Interview Protocol

The researchers also used a researcher-made interview protocol in conducting the face-to-face interview with the participants. An interview protocol was a procedural guide for conducting an interview. It was not just a list of interview questions, it also had a procedural level of interviewing like a script of introduction, the purpose of the research, and request of consent (Jacob S. 2012). The interview protocol was composed of ten (10) semi-structured guide questions that correspond with the information needed to answer the problems of the study.

Procedure

This study utilized a descriptive phenomenological approach to explore the lived experiences of students in single-parent households. The purpose was to illuminate specific experiences to identify the phenomena that were perceived by the actors in a particular situation (Outoshi, 2018). The following procedures show the process by which this study was conducted in three (3) stages: Initial Stage, Actual Procedure, and Final Results.

Initial Stage

The initial stage provided the background of the study where it explained the history or background of the study, as well as the purpose of conducting this research. The researchers then reviewed several related literatures (such as single-parent households, effects on children living in single-parent households, factors affecting students' academic performances and social life, significance of parents' support in children's academic performance) in order to support the study and discuss the relevance of the literature to the study. A theoretical framework was also provided for the purpose of utilizing theories (such as social identity ecological theory) to capture the perspectives of single-parent households.

Actual Procedure

The researchers had nine (9) participants for the interview who fitted the inclusion criteria of any age currently enrolled in Lucrecia R. Kasilag Senior High School and had a single-parent household. Participants were recruited through face-to-face interviews and were evaluated whether they fit the inclusion criteria or not. After the recruitment process, consent was asked from the participants to determine whether they agreed to participate in the study and were asked to sign and read the informed consent form as a proof of agreement. They were also informed beforehand that the entire interview was video recorded for transcription and data analysis purposes. The signed informed consent form was comprised of the study's purpose and the entire process of how the interview progressed. For the interview proper, the researchers utilized the researcher-made questionnaire which was composed of ten (10) main open-ended questions and probe questions. It started by building rapport with the participants by asking light and easy questions. From there on, the main questions were asked subsequently until all the required data was obtained. Moreover, the participants were given enough time to answer and analyze the questions for them to further elaborate their experiences. After the entire interview session, a debriefing process was conducted.

Final Results

Following a verbatim transcription of the interview, the researchers proceeded to present, analyze, and interpret all the data and information they gathered. As soon as they identified and evaluated the presentation they made in the previous chapter, the researchers wrote their conclusion and made recommendations regarding the study's results or findings.

Ethical Considerations

This study followed the ethical guidelines established in the Belmont Report of 1979. These principles were designed to ensure that the data collected were conducted in a proper manner and that the participants were treated with respect. An informed consent process is a vital part of protecting autonomy. It allows researchers to provide potential participants with complete disclosure about the study's nature, risks, benefits, and alternatives.

Before conducting interviews, the researcher obtained written consent from each participant to ensure that they are aware of the nature of the study and its purpose. This consent form included all of the necessary information about the study, such as the expected benefits, the risks involved, and the alternatives to participating. This document describes the procedures that are in place to ensure that the data collected from the study is protected from unauthorized access and disclosure. The researcher also ensures that the data is not linked to the identity of the participants. It clearly states who will be responsible for contacting the individuals about the study and their rights. After reading the consent, the participants were provided with an opportunity to ask questions. The goal of this process was to ensure that the participants were not coerced into participating.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Emergent Themes*

<i>Superordinate Themes</i>	<i>Subordinate Themes</i>	
Challenges Encountered	1.1 Emotional and Supportive Challenges <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1.1 Lack of affection 1.1.2 Limited Help from Family Members 1.1.3 Isolation and Lack of Understanding 	
	1.2 Financial Challenges <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1.2.1 Financial Hardships 1.2.2 Challenges of Having a Single Parent 1.2.3 Role of Being a Provider 1.2.4 Limited Financial Support for Personal Needs 	
	Experiences of Growing Up in a Single-Parent Household	2.1 New Responsibilities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1.1 Taking on Parental Roles
		2.2 Bullying and Social Challenges <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2.2.1 Experiences of Bullying
Emotional Well-Being	3.1 Emotional Struggles <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1.1 Feeling of Envy 	
	3.2 Negative Outlook on Personal Future <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.2.1 Depression and Lack of Motivation 3.2.2 Concerns About Achieving Future Dreams 	
	3.3 Hopes for Future Family Life <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.3.1 Desire for a Complete Family 3.3.2 Intent to Make Wise Relationship Choices 	

Theme 1: Challenges Encountered

1.1 Emotional and Supportive Challenges

1.1.1 Lack of affection

Participants expressed feelings of emotional neglect, often attributing this to the physical absence of one parent. For example, one respondent noted,

“ahmm.. parang normal lang siya, kasi yung mama ko is ofw. Siguro yung oras tsaka yung, yung quality time, yung affection kase hindi ko nakalakihan yung mama ko. Hmm, parang yung kase ano pag buo yung pamilya mo laging pwede mong mayakap tas ganyan, pero pag single yung parent laging wala kase kailangan mag work.” (P6)

According to Marici et al. (2023), while paternal rejection was related to guilt, abuse was associated with both shame and guilt. How children and teenagers viewed themselves in relation to others was influenced by the environments in which they grew up. Similarly, Villarreal (2023) indicated a period of child development in which many parents relied more on boundaries to minimize risks from risky behaviors and negative consequences. Parents who expressed stress negatively when communicating with their adolescent(s) increasingly reflected negative communication patterns. Respectful support created an environment where warmth and affection were welcomed and celebrated. Parenting trends were changing.

1.1.2 Limited Help from Family Members

Many respondents shared experiences of reduced familial support, especially in academic and domestic realms, after the separation of their parents or the migration of one parent.

“Siguro nung lumipat kame dito sa quezon city is ahmm.. Wala na masyadong nakaalalay although andyan naman yung mga ate ko, kase busy din naman sila sa pag aaral nila. Yung sa pag gawa ng mga projects, yung mga pag tulong sa mga gagawin namin is salo ko na talaga kumbaga hindi na, wala nang aasahan kase nga wala nang tutulong.” (P7)

McCarthy et al. (2023) mentioned that when their relative had been originally diagnosed and placed in an institution, the participants felt their hope had been initially undermined. The burden of being a carer and certain mental health providers' poor communication techniques had significantly lowered hope.

However, Dias et al. (2022) stated that receiving social support from family members and teachers, along with having had a friend or family member with Special Educational Needs (SEN), was linked to more positive behavioral and emotional attitudes toward peers who had been identified as having SEN.

1.1.3 Isolation and Lack of Understanding

Feelings of isolation were common among participants. One shared,

“parang growing up parang ano.. parang wala.. parang lumalaki ako na walang.. iniisip ko na wala akong kakampi, wala akong mapag sasabihan. Kung may pag sasabihan man ako, gagamitin nila yon against sayo.. sakin.” (P4)

Halverson (2024) stated that losing supportive relationships with friends and family members could result from an unwillingness to engage in social activities. While social media relationships could help reduce feelings of loneliness, they could not replace in-person interaction and presence. In addition, a study showed that isolated and lonely people experienced a lack of control, but teachers had little understanding of the kind of pedagogy that could help students deal with these feelings (Rippé et al., 2021).

1.2 Financial Challenges

1.2.1 Financial Hardships

The financial burden on single-parent families was a significant concern for participants.

“mahirap as in mahirap kase tulad syempre tulad niyan wala na kong tatay.. wala ng sumusuporta tas si... mama din single parent, ako din single parent diba... eh ngayon parang bumubuhay lang din sa’kin si.. Mama sa.. lalo na sa gastusin ganyan.. mahirap talaga.” (P9)

Furthermore, financial hardship created a stressful situation for single mothers, who might not have had enough income to maintain their current standard of living, had limited savings, and might have needed to find a second job to make ends meet. Financial well-being was a major concern for single mothers. Because it affected not only their quality of life but also their child’s quality of life, this was because they might have been exposed to financial difficulties and pressures, which could have reduced their level of economic well-being (Md Nor et al., 2018). Also, the gendered nature of single parenthood was clear. Single mothers bore the brunt of the burden of raising children alone, making up the highest proportion of single-parent households at 85%. Because most single mothers shouldered the responsibility of raising their children alone, the consequences had profound implications for their finances, social lives, and mental health (Affandy, 2023). It had also consistently been shown that single mothers experienced financial vulnerability compared to the general population (Nor, 2022).

1.2.2 Challenges of Having a Single Parent

The longing for a complete parental unit was a poignant theme, with respondents expressing how the absence of one parent made life more difficult.

“Ano po importante po na ano buo po kayo kumpleto kasi hindi magiging mahirap kung mararanasan ko or ng ganitong klaseng bagay kung andun yung magulang na gumagabay.” (P3)

In findings of another study, everyone who got married and became a parent either wanted or wanted their marriage to end and become a single parent. They certainly wanted to have a full-fledged family, which everyone dreamed of. But sometimes fate had a different will. These ideal conditions could not be maintained forever or realized. Many parents had specific circumstances that required them to care for, raise, and educate their children independently (Listiana, 2021).

Similarly, single-parent families were not always the result of family breakdown, but given the rapid cultural changes in society, they might have been a choice. Possible reasons for an incomplete family structure might have included the death of a parent, divorce or separation of parents, unmarried biological parent, or unmarried adoptive parent (Sangeet & Singh, 2022). In addition, the impact of single parenthood on a child’s development could have been good or bad. But despite the impact single parenting could have had on children, they could grow up to be happy, successful, and well-adjusted individuals. With special care, single parents could raise successful children with excellent overall development in their social and emotional lives (Kelkar & Kapure, 2022).

1.2.3 Role of Being a Provider

Older siblings often had to take on financial responsibilities, particularly in the absence of the father.

“consider na lahat po gagawin ko po para di po sila papabaya kasi kasi po nangako din po ako kay papa na kapag wala po sya ako po yung bahala sa kanila.” (P3)

In addition, the role of older siblings as providers of sibling networks. Older siblings were described as potential caregivers, mentors, and sources of support for younger siblings, nephews, and nieces. They were seen as influential figures in the ‘potential kinship matrix’, facilitating the creation of family relationships and engaging in various forms of support, including financial and practical support (Budginaitė-Mačkinė & Juozeliūnienė, 2023).

In addition, in such families, older siblings took on the role of caring for their younger siblings. Taking on a parenting role unprepared and unsupported placed additional emotional stress on the head of the household and negatively impacted future success (Ntuli, 2020).

1.2.4 Limited Financial Support for Personal Needs

Many respondents discussed the difficulties in meeting personal needs and desires, highlighting the financial limitations of their households.

"ang hirap po mag ano mag hingi ng needs and wants mo po sa ano.. sobra.. lalo na po kung adult kana rin and wala kana naman po work kahit graduating kana man po... Unlike sa.... dalawa po yung magulang mas parang.... lalo na kung okay... mas parang nabibigay yung needs nila." (P5)

Another study said, single-parent families were at higher risk of experiencing financial hardship, which could impact their psychological well-being. Participants described issues of food and fuel shortages and the need to make sacrifices to meet children's basic needs. In some cases, participants were left without food and struggled to survive to pay the bill (Stack & Meredith, 2018). Moreover, financial insecurity was often a top priority for single parents as they had to juggle childcare responsibilities while managing family finances on one income. Studies showed that single-parent families were at higher risk for poverty and might have struggled to provide their children with basic needs such as housing, food, and health care (Echave Rees, 2023).

Theme 2: Experiences of Growing Up in a Single-Parent Household

2.1 New Responsibilities

2.1.1 Taking on Parental Roles

The eldest children often had to assume significant responsibilities, managing household tasks and caring for younger siblings.

"ako po yung panganay eh so tatlo kaming magkapatid ako yung panganay edi yung bali yung responsibilidad ng nanay ko talagang saakin na ano like that ako po yung gumagawa ng dapat na sya po yung gumagawa ganon yung gaya nang ano kunwari sa paglalaba yung pagluluto nagtyatyaga sa pag-aasikaso saamin na dapat sya yung ano tsaka yung responsibilidad nya eh ako na eh para saakin para ako narin yung parang nagtatayong na ano magulang sa kapatid ko." (P3)

Usually, growing up in a single-parent household tended to make children get used to taking responsibilities and making a contribution to the operations in the family. As they understood the significance of sharing responsibility and many showed to enjoy their tasks and contributions (Brennan, n.d.). Students often avoided adding to the burden their single parents had to carry. Naturally, they did more things independently to show others that they could do things on their own (Mahmood, 2023).

2.2 Bullying and Social Challenges

2.2.1 Experiences of Bullying

Participants shared painful experiences of being bullied due to their family situation.

"pag nabubully ako ahh! Or yung di kaya sasabihan ka nila na ahh! Ikaw nga wala kang tatay eh! Eh ikaw nga ano eh! Tawag nito wala kang kinikilalang tatay mo parang ganon tawag nito sa tuwing naririnig ko na ganon syempre masakit din yun tas parang ayun dumadagdag yun sa ano sa emotions ko ayun nalulungkot ganon tas lagi kong hinahanap yung presensya ng tatay ko." (P1)

One discovery said that adolescents living with just one parent were bullied more than those with two parents, even after considering other factors like social and economic background, indicated that a wider social disadvantage could have been a possible reason (Låftman, et al., 2017). In addition, children raised by a single parent experienced situation such as becoming victims of unhealthy relationships, engaging in social vices, and even becoming addicted to social media because of the effects of behavioral issues and challenges with their parents. They often felt less cared for, neglected, or not welcomed unlike the other children (Perera, 2021).

Theme 3: Emotional Well-Being

3.1 Emotional Struggles

3.1.1 Feeling of Envy

A common emotional response among the participants was envy towards peers from two-parent families, especially during public family gatherings.

"nung family day nung elementary, pag nakikita ko yung mga kaklase kong kasama yung papa at mama nila ganon tas ako wala or yung relatives ko lang yung present or yung ate ko." (P6)

In comparison to peers in better situations, children from single-parent households might have felt lesser and envious, especially when there was a large gap in wealth (Fu, 2023). Moreover, most students were hiding the fact that they were being raised by a single parent. A few students also felt inferior to their peers because their single parents struggled to meet the necessities asked by the school (Perera, 2021).

3.2 Negative Outlook on Personal Future

3.2.1 Depression and Lack of Motivation

The stress and sadness from their family circumstances often led to depression and a lack of motivation, particularly affecting their academic performance.

"nung mga fewww few years na nakaraan taon naka apekto sya saakin kasi ano nag parang ano sobrang nadepress ako or or parang ano sobrang lungkot ko dahil nga yun parang wala wala yung papa namin sa tabi namin kasi parang naawa ako sa mama ko sya lang kasi yung bumubuhay saamin and nahihirapan sya ganon." (P2)

Additionally, according to Washington, et al. (2022), college students all faced different challenges to completing schoolwork while balancing work, school, and personal life. Students from single-parent households and students from dual-parent households faced challenges that impacted their mental health differently. Likewise, there was a difference between the single and two-parent students according to the mean of educational attainment, depression, anxiety, stress, and shyness, but there was no significant difference between them in terms of anxiety and aggression. The research findings indicated that the absence of each parent had a negative effect on the children's mental health and educational attainment (Aminian et al., 2018).

3.2.2 Concerns About Achieving Future Dreams

Participants expressed concerns about their ability to achieve their aspirations due to the financial and emotional strains of growing up in a single-parent family.

"since single parent nga po yung mama ko parang nahihirapan po ako mag look forward kung.. kakayanin ko bang maabot tong dreams.. dreams ko na isa lang po siya sa nag pro provide.. parang ang hirap po.. ang hirap po na mag look forward na maabot ko pa kaya to soon." (P8)

According to Shipley (2020), parental involvement had a major impact on a student's educational success, children from two parent families tended to have greater academic achievement and more years of schooling than children of single parent homes. Students expressed that the expectations of their parent, communication about school, and encouragement received from the influence outside of the home were the major factors in their educational success. In another study, the grade point averages of the students in two-parent households were significantly higher than the grade point averages of the students in single-parent households. The household composition did have an impact on student academic achievement (Ficco, 2017). Moreover, single parenthood had been predicted as one of the causes of poor academic performance among school students. Most studies in Western countries reported that children of single-mother and single-father families performed academically lower than children of two-parent families (Mahmood, et al., 2023).

3.3 Hopes for Future Family Life

3.3.1 Desire for a Complete Family

Reflecting on their experiences, many participants expressed a strong desire to create a complete and happy family of their own in the future.

"syempre wala akong tatay so parang gusto ko rin na, sa anak ko na ganun na.. uy gusto ko buo kami kase naranasan ko yung past ko dati ganun yung gusto ko yung happy family." (P9)

Supporting the claims of participants, according to Boyer-Pennington et al. (2018), students from intact homes had more favorable expectations about the quality of their future marriage than students from single- and multiple-divorce homes. Students from multiple-divorce homes reported significantly higher amounts of relationship control than students from other backgrounds. Moreover, society continued to see children raised by a single-parent as problematic and a threat to social order. It added more to their desire for a complete family (Mahmood, 2023).

Society still viewed children raised in single-parent homes as problematic and a threat to social order. They were viewed as exhibiting more negative behaviors than children from two-parent homes (Perera, 2021).

3.3.2 Intent to Make Wise Relationship Choices

Participants emphasized the importance of making prudent choices in relationships to avoid the hardships they faced.

"siguro kailangan mas maging ahh.. gamitin mo yung isip kase pag sa relasyon pag nag padalos dalos ka and sabihin na natin na nakabuo kayo, pwedeng pag hindi pa handa yung lalaki at pwede ka niyang iwan then mapupunta sayo lahat ng responsibilities. So, kailangan prepared mo mentally ano, financially, and physically prepared ka sa relasyon at sa pag papamilya." (P6)

In addition, a study found children whose parents had divorced might have been less comfortable with closeness, more avoidant of others, and had less secure attachment styles than those who did not experience a divorce (Cullen, 2021). In modern society, individuals' emotional health was significantly impacted by the interplay of attachment relationships, self-esteem, and psychological maturity within romantic relationships. The refusal type of attachment relationship, the medium level of self-esteem, and a lower level of coping

with love stress, caring, and interest in love psychological maturity, and their views on love and marriage showed doubts and anxiety about the stability and commitment of a love relationship. However, some of them might have been able to make more sophisticated personal options due to their growth processes, which affected the shaping of their perspectives on marriage and love (Huang et al., 2024).

Conclusions

In this study, the researchers presented the challenges and experiences of individuals growing up in single-parent households. They primarily shared their viewpoints about the emotional, supportive, and financial challenges they encountered, as well as the impact these experiences had on their personal development and future aspirations. Consequently, after assessing these experiences, they learned the complexities and implications of growing up in a single-parent family.

The participants represented the individuals who have navigated significant challenges and demonstrate resilience and adaptability in their circumstances. Based on the above-mentioned findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

Participants faced emotional and supportive challenges, including a lack of affection, limited help from family members, and feelings of isolation. The absence of one parent often led to emotional neglect and a lack of understanding from others. Despite these challenges, they highlighted the importance of respectful support and the evolving nature of parenting trends.

Financial challenges were the significant concern for participants, with many experiencing financial hardships and the burden of being a provider. The absence of one parent often necessitated older siblings taking on financial responsibilities and highlighted the limited financial support for personal needs. These challenges underscored the importance of financial well-being and the gendered nature of single parenthood.

Participants expressed new responsibilities, such as taking on parental roles and managing household tasks. They also faced social challenges, including experiences of bullying due to their family situation. These responsibilities and social challenges shaped their development and coping mechanisms, demonstrating their resilience and adaptability.

The study's central findings shed insight into the emotional well-being and future aspirations of individuals from single-parent households. The values and inputs provided represent the initial step in progressing the understanding of this phenomenon. It has undeniably made a significant contribution to developing action plans that will help support individuals in similar situations, whether it is addressing the root causes of these challenges or empowering people to seek and provide support.

As researchers continue to explore the dynamics of single-parent households, educators and other professionals in this field could produce more accurate and up-to-date information that will serve as the foundation for future research. To educate and enlighten the masses with reliable sources of information and the importance of supportive and inclusive environments. It also highlights the value of addressing the specific emotional struggles and social challenges faced by individuals from single-parent families.

As the field progresses, related professionals may open themselves to discussing social issues and finding ways or solutions for them. Hence, now is the time to enhance traditional approaches, educate, and pursue research in the psychological aspect and actuate on it. Unless experts in the field address the problems brought about by today's world order, it is impossible to discuss achieving sustainable, holistic health among individuals and society.

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